

**THE HARMONY OF ETHICS AND FAMILY UPBRINGING AS A
FACTOR OF THE PURITY OF THE SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT OF
YOUNG PEOPLE**

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Humanity has appeared on the planet earth as a living being, and its progress has never been easy and without obstacles. Echoes of "global" problems that threaten people's lives can be observed in all periods of the evolution of human development. Before talking about global problems, we need to understand the content of this philosophical category. The dictionary meaning of the concept "global" means " general" in French, and "globus - globe" in Latin. So, in both senses, it covers the universal-worldly problems related to the life and fate of mankind.

human society was during the period of "homo habilis" - (literal man), their life was spent in a series of global problems, such as earthquakes, floods, hunger, famine, various epidemic diseases, and tribal wars, which occurred as a result of natural disasters. In the period of human history called " homo sapiens" (conscious man), global problems arose directly as a product of human activity. These are:

- Violation of the purity of the human spiritual environment (problem of ethics),
- Environmental crisis (Ecological problem),
- Related to population growth (Demographic problem)
- Global nuclear arms race on Earth (problem of thermonuclear war)
- Global problems such as ending hunger, poverty, and backwardness (Problem of Urbanization) threaten conscious people.

The problem of "ethics" is a problem that destroys human spirituality and its purity in society at present, in particular, it arises as a result of the spiritual poverty of people's minds and leads the whole society to spiritual decline (drug addiction, alcoholism, obscenity, political terrorism, economic terrorism, such as corruption) is a concept that summarizes a set of vices. For this reason, this problem is on the front page of global problems.

One of our main goals today is to create "Ethics" in society - scientific trends against the violation of the purity of the spiritual environment of people and to preserve the purity of the spiritual consciousness of our citizens (mainly young people). depends on spiritual consciousness and worldview.

The spiritual and moral education carried out is the main link to ensuring the purity of the spiritual environment in the society. The past of mankind shows that no human child ever came into the world spiritually. The level of spiritual consciousness in each individual is at the same level at the time of their birth, that is, blank and pure like a white sheet of paper. goes, that is, as much as a person needs material goods (such as housing, food, clothes) upon entering the world, he feels the same need for education. In the past, when one of the intellectuals went to a famous scholar and asked if I could start teaching him life lessons when my son turned two years old, he said, "You are two years late in educating your son." The zero answers should be an example for all of us. So, if we conclude from the above points that the educational process is leading to maintain the purity of spirituality in society (in particular, the purity of the spirituality of the youth), where and in what forms the spiritual education carried out is one of the main problems that require a solution.

It is known that the family, preschool educational institutions, schools, neighborhoods, and higher educational institutions are among the institutions that implement the educational process in society. These institutions are engaged in the education of the young generation. It is no exaggeration to say that upbringing in the family environment is the prelude to preserving the purity of the spiritual environment of society and its youth. Because "society" and "family" are closely related to each other, society cannot exist without families, and family also exists within society. If the family faces spiritual poverty, society will also experience a spiritual crisis, if the family is highly spiritual, various foreign and morally corrupt ideas cannot enter the society. The spiritual wealth of society is summed up by the sum of the spiritual wealth of people in it. It is clear from this that not only the problem of ethics but also the solution to other problems occurring in society is laid in the family, that is, any education starts from the family.

To raise young people with high spirituality in the family environment, they should instill in their minds "patriotism", "goodness", "justice", "harmony", "wisdom", "kindness", "correctness" in the words of Zoroastrians. it is necessary to inculcate good ideas such as eloquence", "and morality". Such spiritual and moral ideas are brought to the minds of young people by the family's senior representatives using the methods of education such as "story", "explanation", "conversation", "admonition", "instruction" and "training". is absorbed through Young people instilled with the ideals of goodness in the family, before reaching school age, reach the level of distinguishing between what is good and what is

bad, what is honest and what is unclean, and in their worldview, immunity is formed against morally corrupt vices such as drunkenness, drunkenness, and terrorism. keeps going With these aspects, family education plays a fundamental role in the fight against the problem of ethics.

At the end of our opinion, our president Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "It is to further strengthen the foundations of the family, which is sacred to us, to create an atmosphere of peace, calmness, harmony and mutual respect in households, to fill spiritual and educational work with concrete content. We would like to emphasize how important the words "must be".

